

Supplementary Table S1. Alphabetical list of the salangid species with GenBank accession numbers of the nucleotide sequences used in this study

Species	GenBank accession number	Reference
<i>Hemisanx brachyrostralis</i> *	KJ645979	[1]
<i>Leucosoma chinensis</i> *	MW131880	[2]
<i>Leucosoma reevesii</i> 28S rRNA	HQ915907	[3]
<i>Leucosoma reevesii</i> RAG1	HQ916075	[3]
<i>Leucosoma reevesii</i> zic1	HQ916205	[3]
<i>Leucosoma reevesii</i> ENC1	HQ915993	[3]
<i>Leucosoma reevesii</i> RNF213	HQ916119	[3]
<i>Leucosoma reevesii</i> glyt	HQ916033	[3]
<i>Leucosoma reevesii</i> SH3PX3	HQ916160	[3]
<i>Neosalangichthys ishikawae</i> CytB	HQ915937 - HQ915939	[3]
<i>Neosalangichthys ishikawae</i> 28S rRNA	HQ915892	[3]
<i>Neosalangichthys ishikawae</i> RAG1	HQ916060	[3]
<i>Neosalangichthys ishikawae</i> zic1	HQ916190	[3]
<i>Neosalangichthys ishikawae</i> ENC1	HQ915979	[3]
<i>Neosalangichthys ishikawae</i> RNF213	HQ916105	[3]
<i>Neosalangichthys ishikawae</i> glyt	HQ916021	[3]
<i>Neosalangichthys ishikawae</i> SH3PX3	HQ916147	[3]
<i>Neosalanx anderssoni</i> *	HM106492	[4]
<i>Neosalanx anderssoni</i> CytB	HQ915916 - HQ915919	[3]
<i>Neosalanx anderssoni</i> 28S rRNA	HQ915872	[3]
<i>Neosalanx anderssoni</i> RAG1	HQ916043	[3]
<i>Neosalanx anderssoni</i> zic1	HQ916170	[3]
<i>Neosalanx anderssoni</i> ENC1	HQ915961	[3]
<i>Neosalanx anderssoni</i> RNF213	HQ916085	[3]
<i>Neosalanx anderssoni</i> glyt	HQ916003	[3]
<i>Neosalanx anderssoni</i> SH3PX3	HQ916127	[3]
<i>Neosalanx argentea</i> CytB	DQ191080 - DQ191081	[5]
<i>Neosalanx brevirostris</i> CytB	HQ915921 - HQ915924	[3]
<i>Neosalanx brevirostris</i> 28S rRNA	HQ915876	[3]
<i>Neosalanx brevirostris</i> RAG1	HQ916045	[3]
<i>Neosalanx brevirostris</i> zic1	HQ916174	[3]

<i>Neosalanx brevirostris ENC1</i>	HQ915965	[3]
<i>Neosalanx brevirostris RNF213</i>	HQ916089	[3]
<i>Neosalanx brevirostris glyt</i>	HQ916007	[3]
<i>Neosalanx brevirostris SH3PX3</i>	HQ916131	[3]
<i>Neosalanx jordani CytB</i>	HQ915932 - HQ915936	[3]
<i>Neosalanx jordani CytB</i>	EU656114 - EU656132	[6]
<i>Neosalanx jordani CytB</i>	DQ191082	[5]
<i>Neosalanx jordani 28S rRNA</i>	HQ915890	[3]
<i>Neosalanx jordani RAG1</i>	HQ916058	[3]
<i>Neosalanx jordani zic1</i>	HQ916188	[3]
<i>Neosalanx jordani ENC1</i>	HQ915977	[3]
<i>Neosalanx jordani RNF213</i>	HQ916103	[3]
<i>Neosalanx jordani glyt</i>	HQ916019	[3]
<i>Neosalanx jordani SH3PX3</i>	HQ916145	[3]
<i>Neosalanx oligodontis CytB</i>	DQ191083 - DQ191086	[5]
<i>Neosalanx pseudotaihuensis CytB</i>	HM151563 - HM151565	[7]
<i>Neosalanx pseudotaihuensis CytB</i>	DQ191090 - DQ191092	[5]
<i>Neosalanx reganius CytB</i>	DQ191093	[5]
<i>Neosalanx taihuensis CytB</i>	MK523757 - MK523765	[8]
<i>Neosalanx taihuensis CytB</i>	MK354263 - MK354270	[9]
<i>Neosalanx taihuensis CytB</i>	EU376454 - EU376489	[10]
<i>Neosalanx taihuensis CytB</i>	DQ191094 - DQ191111	[5]
<i>Neosalanx taihuensis*</i>	MH348204	[11]
<i>Neosalanx taihuensis*</i>	MW291630	[12]
<i>Neosalanx taihuensis*</i>	JX524196	[13]
<i>Neosalanx tangkahkeii CytB</i>	DQ191112	[5]
<i>Neosalanx tangkahkeii*</i>	KP170510	[14]
<i>Plecoglossus altivelis*</i>	AB047553	[15]
<i>Plecoglossus altivelis 28S rRNA</i>	HQ915910	[3]
<i>Plecoglossus altivelis RAG1</i>	HQ916078	[3]
<i>Plecoglossus altivelis zic1</i>	HQ916208	[3]
<i>Plecoglossus altivelis ENC1</i>	HQ915997	[3]

<i>Plecoglossus altivelis RNF213</i>	HQ916122	[3]
<i>Plecoglossus altivelis glyt</i>	HQ916036	[3]
<i>Plecoglossus altivelis SH3PX3</i>	HQ916163	[3]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis*</i>	HM106494	[4]
<i>Protosalanx hyalocranius*</i>	KJ499917	[16]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis*</i>	KP306787	[17]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis*</i>	MH330683	[18]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis*</i>	MW291629	[19]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis 28S rRNA</i>	HQ915868	[3]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis RAG1</i>	HQ916039	[3]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis zic1</i>	HQ916166	[3]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis ENC1</i>	HQ915957	[3]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis RNF213</i>	HQ916081	[3]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis glyt</i>	HQ915999	[3]
<i>Protosalanx chinensis SH3PX3</i>	HQ916125	[3]
<i>Retropinna retropinna*</i>	AP004108	[20]
<i>Salangichthys microdon*</i>	AP004109	[20]
<i>Salangichthys microdon 28S rRNA</i>	HQ915895	[3]
<i>Salangichthys microdon RAG1</i>	HQ916063	[3]
<i>Salangichthys microdon zic1</i>	HQ916193	[3]
<i>Salangichthys microdon ENC1</i>	HQ915982	[3]
<i>Salangichthys microdon RNF213</i>	HQ916107	[3]
<i>Salangichthys microdon glyt</i>	HQ916024	[3]
<i>Salangichthys microdon SH3PX3</i>	HQ916150	[3]
<i>Salanx ariakensis*</i>	AP006231	[21]
<i>Salanx ariakensis*</i>	KM517200	[22]
<i>Salanx ariakensis 28S rRNA</i>	HQ915899	[3]
<i>Salanx ariakensis RAG1</i>	HQ916066	[3]
<i>Salanx ariakensis zic1</i>	HQ916196	[3]
<i>Salanx ariakensis ENC1</i>	HQ915985	[3]
<i>Salanx ariakensis RNF213</i>	HQ916110	[3]
<i>Salanx ariakensis glyt</i>	HQ916026	[3]
<i>Salanx ariakensis SH3PX3</i>	HQ916152	[3]
<i>Salanx cuvieri*</i>	KJ645978	[23]

*Mitogenome sequence. The gene name follows the species name.

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